

ADAPTIVE COMBINATION OF LMS AND LOGISTIC-LINEAR EQUALIZERS TO IMPROVE THE SPEED-PERFORMANCE COMPROMISE

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ABSTRACT

The Least Mean Squares algorithm (LMS) has been the most usual solution to channel equalization: it is easy to implement and it is relatively simple to obtain the appropriate parameters to assure stability and convergence. The convergence speed of LMS is high and it is robust in nonstationary channels. Furthermore, the computational burden of this algorithm is very low, and it can be implemented in low computational power processors, while nonlinear algorithms cannot.

The main drawback of this algorithm is that its final Bit Error Rate (BER) is sensitive to the adaptation step and to the effect of well-classified samples which are far from the classification border. Also, in nonlinear channels its performance is reduced.

A sigmoidal nonlinearity applied to the output of the filter can reduce the misadjustment due to well-classified samples, and also reduce the dependence from the adaptation step, although it makes the equalizer much less robust.

We introduce a new scheme based on an adaptive combination of an standard LMS equalizer and a sigmoidal output based equalizer, which benefits from the advantages of both equalizers reducing their drawbacks.

1 INTRODUCTION

It is a well-known fact in Statistics that adding a sigmoidal nonlinearity to a linear model improves the classification performance in binary problems (Logit model) due to a reduction of weights changes for clearly classified samples. This has been the origin of including these activations (or their equivalent tanh version) at the output of neural networks also used for binary classification. On the other hand, it has been repeatedly remarked that equalizing digital channels is basically a classification problem [1], and that nonlinear classifiers give better BER [2], [3], but design, convergence and tracking difficulties have precluded their application, including that of the very simple and relatively efficient Logit model.

In the later case, problems are mainly related to tracking capabilities: qualitatively reasoning and simulation experiments show that the attainable BER when applying gradient adaptation for these schemes is less sensitive to adaptation steps than the classical equalizers having a linear output, due to the inclusion of an additional factor $(1 - o^2)$ in the gradient function

$$\Delta_{w(Logit)}e^2 = 2\mu_1\gamma(d - o_{Logit})(1 - o_{Logit}^2)\mathbf{x} \quad (1)$$

with respect to the standard LMS

$$\Delta_{w(LMS)}e^2 = 2\mu_2\gamma(d - o_{LMS})\mathbf{x} \quad (2)$$

where e is the error, μ the adaptation step, d the desired signal (transmitted or decided) symbol, γ the tanh slope at the origin, $\mathbf{x}$ the channel output sample vector and o the equalizer output. For the LMS equalizer $o = \mathbf{w}^T\mathbf{x}$ and for the Logit equalizer $o = \tanh(\gamma\mathbf{w}^T\mathbf{x})$, $\mathbf{w}$ being the filter weights. The factor $(d - o_{Logit})$ also provides less sensitivity to the adaptation steps because $\|o_{Logit}\| < 1$, so it will be advantageous to apply the Kullback-Leibler cost function [4], which leads to the gradient

$$\Delta_{w(Logit)}H = 2\mu_1\gamma(d - o_{Logit})\mathbf{x} \quad (3)$$

Logit output allows some freedom in selecting μ , thus offering more possibilities for an adequate balance between convergence speed and final BER (degree of convergence). The sigmoidal function tanh requires an exponential function computation, which needs a relatively high computational cost, but it can be replaced by approximate functions that need fewer computations. The simplest example is a saturated linear function.

Two are the drawbacks of applying sigmoidal activations. First, output o is got from a tanh operation. This means that samples that are far from the classification border do not contribute to adaptation. This fact is desirable in a stationary situation, as these samples do not carry important information to the equalizer and

Figure 1: The proposed equalizer

increase misadjustment; but when a nonstationarity appears, these samples can give important information for tracking. Second, the tanh function may have "stopping" effects. This can be seen when the tanh slope γ is too large and the samples of both classes are mainly nonoverlapped. When the classification border is near to the convergence situation, $(d - o_{Logit}) \approx 0$ for almost all samples, as they will be too far from the classification border. Then, the adaptation will stop. Obviously, the same holds for the term $(1 - o^2)$. Both effects are potential sources for tracking losses, as observed in the practice.

So, and in the same way as other proposals to combine cost functions [5], [6], to combine a standard LMS with a (gradient) Logit equalizer will be interesting if the result combines the low final BER of the Logit structure at a high convergence speed with the high LMS tracking capabilities. Unfortunately, the proposed combination schemes for other cost functions do not provide much insight on how to proceed: they are based on hypothesis about samples or just empirical procedures. Consequently, their extension is not easy.

2 ADAPTIVE COMBINATION OF LMS AND LOGIT EQUALIZERS

We propose to apply a scheme based on an adaptive linear combination of two equalizers, a conventional LMS and a Logit based equalizer. The whole scheme is shown in Figure 1.

The LMS and Logit outputs are fed into a joint decision step, after applying a tanh to the LMS output, in order to compensate for the magnitude differences that can appear between the two outputs.

Weights of the final connections are λ and $1 - \lambda$ ($0 < \lambda < 1$) respectively. Obviously, when $\lambda = 1$ the decision is driven by the LMS output, and when $\lambda = 0$, by the Logit output.

In order to achieve the adequate value of λ at each

time, it is adapted by means of a gradient algorithm that uses the final output error. In stationary conditions, the Logit scheme will offer the lowest error, so λ will decrease, but when both equalizers track a change in the channel, LMS will have the lowest error, because LMS is better for tracking, and λ will increase.

The adaptation step of λ has to be large enough to assure adequate speed, but the instantaneous value of λ has to be restricted between 0 and 1. Also, in order to remove the noise effect of λ when switching from an output to the other, instead of feedbacking the final decision to the equalizers, a hysteresis function has been applied to λ : if λ increases to a given value λ_1 , then the LMS output is chosen to decide the symbol for decision directed training; if λ decreases to a value $\lambda_0 < \lambda_1$, then the Logit output is chosen. λ_0 and λ_1 have to be empirically found, in order not to introduce delay, but their values are not critical.

We use the decision obtained from the hysteresis operation to train the Logit filter from the estimated error of its output. To train the LMS there are two options: using the decision from the hysteresis or using always the decision obtained directly from the LMS output. The first one can have less error probability than the second and using it can slightly reduce the filter misadjustment; but a delay in the change of λ in presence of channel variations may result in a tracking loss. If the LMS output is used, the number of decision errors may be higher in a stationary situation, but it will track faster the channel nonstationarities. Consequently, this is the way in which the LMS has been trained in the simulations.

3 SIMULATIONS

Simulations of LMS, Logit and the combined equalizers for linear and nonlinear channels with memory have been made. The following examples are representative of general results. A linear channel had two FIR sections with weights 1, 0.3, -0.2, 0.3, 0.2, -0.1 and 1, -0.3, -0.77, 0.144, 0.133, -0.0014. The first FIR simulates the transmitter impulse response and the second one is a typical multipath channel impulse response. To simulate nonstationarities, the second channel was changed during the decision directed procedure. The hysteresis values were set to $\lambda_0 = 0$ and $\lambda_1 = 0.2$.

A nonlinear channel consisted of the first linear section followed by a nonlinearity of the type

$$\xi \|x_{max}\| \tanh\left(\frac{x}{\xi \|x_{max}\|}\right) \quad (4)$$

simulating a power amplifier with saturation effects in a multipath propagation free channel. x_{max} is the maximum input signal absolute amplitude. $\xi \|x_{max}\|$ was set to produce a compression of 20%.

Equalizers had order 9. For the Logit filter, the Kullback-Leibler cost function has been used, as it provides less computational cost and slightly higher robust-

ness, because term $(1 - o^2)$ does not appear in the gradient. The tanh slope was $\gamma = 5$

Figure 2: BER performance respect to the adaptation step, linear channel; o: proposed equalizer; +: LMS. (See Subsection 3.1)

Figure 3: BER performance respect to the adaptation step, nonlinear channel; o: proposed equalizer; +: LMS. (See Subsection 3.1)

3.1 Dependence of μ

The BER performance for 10 values of μ from 3.5×10^{-4} to 2×10^{-2} was tested for a SNR of 13 dB in the linear channel and 15 dB in the nonlinear one. Results are shown in Figures 2 and 3.

3.2 Convergence Speed

The convergence speed for the LMS and the proposed equalizer has been tested. Simulations are: the proposed

equalizer and the LMS with all adaptation steps for minimum BER and LMS with the adaptation step which produces the same convergence speed as the proposed equalizer. Figure 4 show that the proposed equalizer has a much smaller convergence time than LMS with the same final BER. LMS with same convergence speed as the proposed has an error of about four times the one of Combination in the linear channel.

Figure 4: Convergence of the proposed and the LMS equalizers for minimum BER, and LMS for the same speed as the proposed, linear channel (See Subsection 3.2)

Figure 5: BER vs. SNR; o: proposed equalizer, +: LMS with the minimum BER, x: LMS with the same speed as the proposed equalizer, linear channel. (See subsection 3.3)

3.3 BER performance

To compute BER performance, the same values of adaptation step as in Subsection 3.2 have been chosen. Results are shown in Figures 5 and 6 for both linear and nonlinear channels. The improvement over the LMS is up to 1 dB in the linear channel, and up to 2 dB in the nonlinear one. Comparisons have been made for equalizers with equal convergence speed (choosing the

Figure 6: BER vs. SNR; o: proposed equalizer, +: LMS with the minimum BER, $\times$: LMS with the same speed as the proposed equalizer. Nonlinear channel. (See subsection 3.3)

Figure 7: Behaviour of the three (Logit, LMS, and its combination) proposed equalizer outputs when there is an abrupt channel change (see Subsection 3.4)

appropriate values for adaptation steps). For the Logit equalizer the BER performance is the same as that of the proposed equalizer.

3.4 Tracking

Tracking losses rates for the linear nonstationary channels have also been measured. As an example, where the channel had the same structure as the linear one in the previous experiments, but the second and third weights were changed from -0.3 to $+0.15$ and from -0.77 to $+0.38$ respectively during the decision directed training period (3000 samples after the supervised period, which consists of 1000 samples), the proposed equalizer has the same performance as the LMS: around 0 to 2.5% tracking losses (over 1000 realizations) for $\mu = 10^{-3}$ to 10^{-2} and for SNR=10 to 20 dB. The Logit equalizer shows much more losses (between 25 and 35%) for the same parameters.

Figure 7 shows the BER behaviour of the three equal-

izer outputs. It can be observed that during the channel change, the combination follows the LMS BER until the Logit BER falls, then the combination changes to Logit.

4 CONCLUSION

We have introduced an adaptive combined equalizer based on the error minimization of the joint output of a standard LMS and a Logit equalizers. The equalizer provides the advantages of both of them reducing their drawbacks. The equalizer has the tracking capabilities of LMS and the good compromise between BER and convergence speed of a Logit based equalizer, which has a relative independence from the adaptation step. The combined equalizer performance in presence of nonlinearities clearly improves the LMS performance.

The computational burden is not significantly increased and, in preliminary experiments, we have seen that the tanh function can be replaced by a saturated linear function, thus reducing dramatically the number of computations per sample needed by the Logit.

The results of the proposed algorithm open the door to other analog procedures including simpler versions with just one filter to reduce the computational burden and extensions to multilevel complex constellations.

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